

Appendix C

Existing Selected River Gauging Stations Data

LIST OF EXHIBITS

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SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 041001 RIVIERE DES MATHEUX – ARCAHAIE	C-22
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HAITI – GIS-Based Hydropower Potential Mapping

SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 060601 RIVIERE CAVAILLON – CAVAILLON	C-26
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SELECTED GAUGING STATIONS LIST

SITE ID	RIVER NAME
010501	Grande Riviere du Nord
020111	Riviere d'Ennery
020701	Riviere Trois Rivières
020702	Riviere Trois Rivières
020703	Riviere Trois Rivières
030101	Riviere de Montrouis
030201	Riviere de l'Artibonite
030202	Riviere de l'Artibonite
030211	Riviere Bois
030221	Riviere la Theme
030231	Riviere Fer a Cheval
030241	Riviere Onde Verte
030251	Riviere Guayamouc
030252	Riviere Bouyaha
030404	Riviere Saint Marc
040201	Riviere Momance
040501	Riviere Grise
040601	Riviere Blanche
040801	Riviere Torcelle
040901	Riviere Coujol
041001	Riviere des Matheux
050201	Riviere Jacmel
050401	Riviere Marigot
060501	Ravine du Sud
060601	Riviere cavaillon
060801	Riviere Cotes de Fer
070201	Riviere Voldrogue
070301	Riviere Grande Anse
099999	Peligre

LEGEND

- Gauging Station Watershed
- Gauging Station
- Cities
- Capital
- Chef Lieu
- Departements
- Rivers
- Roads
- Lakes

HAITI - SELECTED RIVER GAUGING STATIONS AND WATERSHEDS FOR CALIBRATION

MODELED VERSUS HISTORICAL FLOW - MONTHLY AVERAGE VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

Gauge	Flow	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
010501	Modeled	4.4606	3.9026	2.4917	2.9869	8.5073	10.6644	6.3423	6.5042	10.5608	10.7198	11.5433	8.2461
010501	Historical	4.2406	4.2494	4.5869	3.6461	9.9085	11.1775	5.2739	6.4051	8.7263	7.7280	13.0528	7.9356

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	600.00	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	70.54	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	356.95	(mm)
PSUB	0.85	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWLF	0.30	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.09	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	7.60	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- Station
- Watershed
- Cities
- Chef Lieu
- Capital
- Roads
- Rivers
- Departements

SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 010501 GRANDE RIVIERE DU NORD - PONT PAROIS

MODELED VERSUS HISTORICAL FLOW - MONTHLY AVERAGE VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

GAUGE	FLOW	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
020111	Modeled	0.3851	0.3128	0.1986	0.2466	0.6359	0.9074	0.5216	0.6440	1.0552	1.2214	1.0486	0.5618
020111	Historical	0.3727	0.2779	0.2462	0.2963	0.7848	0.9150	0.6019	0.6572	0.9908	0.8157	1.0615	0.7185

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	191.92	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	69.95	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	263.01	(mm)
PSUB	0.95	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWFL	0.11	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.11	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.03	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	0.00	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- River Gauging Station (Green square)
- Watershed (Orange outline)
- Station (Green square)
- Cities (Red star)
- Chef Lieu (Red star with dot)
- Capital (Red star with dot)
- Roads (Red line)
- Rivers (Blue line)
- Departements (Yellow dashed outline)

SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 020111 RIVIERE D'ENNERY - PASSE JOLY

MODELED VERSUS HISTORICAL FLOW - MONTHLY AVERAGE VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

GAUGE	FLOW	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
020702	Modeled	4.6633	4.4361	3.2774	4.3639	6.0868	7.3069	5.1239	5.6997	7.7501	8.5306	9.5277	6.3839
020702	Historical	4.6754	4.3175	3.1854	4.9200	6.7269	5.4699	4.1136	4.0297	6.1140	7.5960	14.6558	7.3462

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	273.23	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	68.56	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	283.31	(mm)
PSUB	0.80	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWf	0.35	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.04	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	34.80	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- Cities
- Chef Lieu
- Capital
- Roads
- Rivers
- Departements
- Station
- Watershed
- River Gauging Station

MODELED VERSUS HISTORICAL FLOW - MONTHLY AVERAGE VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

Gauge	Flow	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
020703	Modeled	0.4947	0.4494	0.3207	0.4277	0.7771	1.0320	0.5813	0.7316	1.1367	1.2538	1.2987	0.7088
020703	Historical	0.3869	0.4573	0.3006	0.3112	0.7859	0.4323	0.4591	0.8781	1.1711	1.2185	2.0328	0.7791

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	51.20	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	69.22	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	234.11	(mm)
PSUB	0.70	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWf	0.30	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.05	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	15.00	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- River Gauging Station
- Watershed
- Station
- Cities
- Chef Lieu
- Capital
- Roads
- Rivers
- Departements

SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 020703 RIVIERE TROIS RIVIERES - PLAISANCE

MODELED VERSUS HISTORICAL FLOW - MONTHLY AVERAGE VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

GAUGE	FLOW	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
030201	Modeled	32.1678	34.6677	30.1878	88.3134	175.3174	156.2673	99.7818	146.7523	170.8539	163.1969	73.3639	45.2441
030201	Historical	35.2816	29.1046	36.1079	41.8112	141.5808	162.1087	123.6927	119.9103	166.5568	188.8502	113.5344	57.5752

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	8,704.41	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	72.63	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	264.40	(mm)
PSUB	0.80	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWf	0.35	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.16	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	21.78	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- River Gauging Station
- Watershed
- Station
- Cities
- Chef Lieu
- Roads
- Rivers
- Departements

SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 030201 RIVIERE DE L'ARTIBONITE - PONT SONDE

Gauge	Flow	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
030202	Modeled	19.0280	21.1058	18.6340	68.8582	155.8721	129.7294	75.2046	121.1267	146.6521	135.3425	59.4082	27.3954
030202	Historical	27.5896	22.0383	18.7374	32.5888	135.7102	142.5939	96.2261	88.5158	128.6421	147.9506	91.7960	45.9686

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	7,473.50	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	71.95	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	265.98	(mm)
PSUB	0.80	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWf	0.35	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.20	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	15.95	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- Cities
- Chef Lieu
- Capital
- Roads
- Rivers
- Departements
- Station
- Watershed
- River Gauging Station

SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 030202 RIVIERE DE L'ARTIBONITE - MIREBALAIS

Gauge	Flow	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
030211	Modeled	1.0842	1.1184	0.9231	1.8530	2.6783	2.8105	2.6344	2.8074	3.0544	2.9808	2.1726	1.4724
030211	Historical	1.1673	1.0420	0.9995	1.2117	1.7878	2.7097	2.5822	2.9604	3.4259	3.9117	2.2712	1.5200

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	67.51	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	77.95	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	224.00	(mm)
PSUB	0.80	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWf	0.30	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.08	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	87.00	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- River Gauging Station
- Watershed
- Station
- Cities
- Chef Lieu
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- Rivers
- Departements

SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 030211 RIVIERE BOIS - VERRETTES

MODELED VERSUS HISTORICAL FLOW - MONTHLY AVERAGE VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

Gauge	Flow	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
030241	Modeled	1.2177	1.3401	1.3038	2.7205	3.0910	2.8713	2.3811	3.0283	3.1955	3.1438	2.6313	1.6849
030241	Historical	1.6230	1.5594	1.6327	1.5546	1.9529	1.9487	2.5336	3.2083	3.5103	3.4625	2.9258	2.6980

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	41.66	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	71.53	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	224.00	(mm)
PSUB	0.70	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWF	0.30	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.09	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	180.00	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- Station
- Watershed
- Cities
- Chef Lieu
- Capital
- Roads
- Rivers
- Departements

SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 030241 RIVIERE ONDE VERTE - ONDE VERTE

Gauge	Flow	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
030251	Modeled	3.7614	4.0406	3.2114	9.5531	46.5488	40.5908	20.1875	32.2534	41.1792	35.1217	19.7266	5.3497
030251	Historical	5.4752	5.1969	4.9975	7.9312	42.6241	52.5953	26.7573	24.8637	35.1353	30.2054	17.6544	8.0852

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	1,970.99	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	73.33	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	274.83	(mm)
PSUB	0.80	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWf	0.35	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.26	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	10.00	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- River Gauging Station (Green square)
- Watershed (Pink outline)
- Station (Green square)
- Cities (Red star)
- Chef Lieu (Red star with dot)
- Capital (Red star with dot)
- Roads (Red line)
- Rivers (Blue line)
- Departements (Yellow outline)

SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 030251 RIVIERE GUAYAMOUC - HINCHE

MODELED VERSUS HISTORICAL FLOW - MONTHLY AVERAGE VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

GAUGE	FLOW	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
030252	Modeled	2.1681	2.2220	1.6242	2.4692	4.5170	4.5730	2.8331	3.5958	4.4255	4.4465	4.5520	3.2876
030252	Historical	2.0319	1.9536	2.1277	1.9996	5.8311	4.2844	2.7571	1.9207	3.3747	4.6918	6.0012	3.7396

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	156.56	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	69.15	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	297.27	(mm)
PSUB	0.80	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWFL	0.30	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.18	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	39.00	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- River Gauging Station
- Watershed
- Station
- Cities
- Chef Lieu
- Capital
- Roads
- Rivers
- Departements

SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 030252 RIVIERE BOUYAHA - SAINT-RAPHAEL

MODELED VERSUS HISTORICAL FLOW - MONTHLY AVERAGE VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

Gauge	Flow	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
030404	Modeled	0.1222	0.1180	0.0896	0.1694	0.2607	0.2891	0.2632	0.3175	0.4188	0.4564	0.2793	0.1760
030404	Historical	0.2418	0.2172	0.2004	0.2342	0.2207	0.2502	0.2789	0.2865	0.2871	0.2199	0.2426	0.2811

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	57.00	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	75.97	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	224.00	(mm)
PSUB	0.80	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWf	0.30	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.00	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	9.84	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

- LEGEND**
- River Gauging Station
 - Watershed
 - Station
 - Cities
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 - Departements

SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 030404 RIVIERE SAINT MARC - CORBAY

MODELED VERSUS HISTORICAL FLOW - MONTHLY AVERAGE VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

Gauge	Flow	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
040201	Modeled	2.0108	2.2606	2.2355	6.2441	8.9249	7.3408	6.1499	8.2636	8.6147	9.8830	5.2324	2.6280
040201	Historical	2.2136	1.9329	1.8172	2.6087	6.2676	8.5338	6.7487	8.2249	10.4079	11.4811	6.3559	3.1965

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	239.53	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	70.02	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	266.38	(mm)
PSUB	0.80	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWf	0.20	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.27	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	30.60	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- River Gauging Station
- Watershed
- Station
- Cities
- Chef Lieu
- Capital
- Roads
- Rivers
- Departements

SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 040201 RIVIERE MOMANCE - BUSSONNIERE

MODELED VERSUS HISTORICAL FLOW - MONTHLY AVERAGE VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

Gauge	Flow	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
040501	Modeled	1,5741	1,6200	1,4786	3,8223	5,2127	4,1697	3,3481	4,7409	5,3785	6,5567	3,6839	2,0562
040501	Historical	2,0003	1,6323	1,4489	1,6887	4,0280	4,8386	3,5325	4,3587	5,6345	6,4250	5,2113	2,8425

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	275.39	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	69.68	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	261.07	(mm)
PSUB	0.90	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWf	0.10	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.14	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	8.70	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- River Gauging Station
- Watershed
- Station
- Cities
- Chef Lieu
- Capital
- Roads
- Rivers
- Departements

MODELED VERSUS HISTORICAL FLOW - MONTHLY AVERAGE VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

Gauge	Flow	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
040601	Modeled	1.4071	1.3210	1.0851	1.5658	1.6401	1.7010	1.3722	1.7540	2.3033	2.9292	2.3228	1.8261
040601	Historical	1.8479	1.5923	1.4295	1.2900	1.5017	1.5049	1.5118	1.6127	2.0105	2.5864	2.2759	2.0650

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	174.19	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	71.24	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	242.42	(mm)
PSUB	0.95	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWF	0.10	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.01	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	0.75	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- River Gauging Station
- Watershed
- Station
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SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 040601 RIVIÈRE BLANCHE - LA GORGE

MODELED VERSUS HISTORICAL FLOW - MONTHLY AVERAGE VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

Gauge	Flow	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
040801	Modeled	0.4611	0.4858	0.4249	1.0447	1.3984	1.3506	1.1930	1.4482	1.6568	1.6872	1.0729	0.6350
040801	Historical	0.4571	0.4488	0.4181	0.5408	1.0618	1.5152	1.4200	1.6774	1.8739	1.8041	1.0346	0.6059

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	74.38	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	77.53	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	232.84	(mm)
PSUB	0.90	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWF	0.30	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.10	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	24.88	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- River Gauging Station
- Watershed
- Station
- Cities
- Chef Lieu
- Capital
- Roads
- Rivers
- Departements

MODELED VERSUS HISTORICAL FLOW - MONTHLY AVERAGE VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

Gauge	Flow	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
040901	Modeled	0.6380	0.6204	0.5019	0.9757	1.1045	1.2800	1.1564	1.4966	1.8176	1.9080	1.3474	0.8947
040901	Historical	0.6085	0.4905	0.4873	0.5062	1.0053	1.6818	1.6515	1.8206	1.8142	1.7604	1.1561	0.7589

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	77.71	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	76.99	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	224.87	(mm)
PSUB	0.90	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWf	0.30	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.03	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	24.00	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- River Gauging Station
- Watershed
- Station
- Cities
- Chef Lieu
- Capital
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- Rivers
- Departements

SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 040901 RIVIERE COUJOL - BASSIN PROBY

MODELED VERSUS HISTORICAL FLOW - MONTHLY AVERAGE VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

Gauge	Flow	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
041001	Modeled	0.5956	0.6118	0.4884	1.1599	1.4971	1.6451	1.3997	1.8468	2.0874	2.1016	1.3461	0.8022
041001	Historical	0.6755	0.6009	0.5420	0.5960	0.8296	1.2925	1.9858	2.4458	2.0298	2.3132	1.3802	0.8909

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	71.39	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	75.35	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	224.00	(mm)
PSUB	0.80	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWf	0.20	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.11	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	18.50	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- Station
- Watershed
- Cities
- Chef Lieu
- Capital
- Roads
- Rivers
- Departements

MODELED VERSUS HISTORICAL FLOW - MONTHLY AVERAGE VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

Gauge	Flow	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
050201	Modeled	0.6959	0.6502	0.6915	4.0091	6.5771	3.8891	2.0230	5.3026	6.0443	8.9740	3.3517	0.9912
050201	Historical	0.7960	0.4817	0.5380	1.6283	6.9390	3.7537	2.1785	8.7767	6.0014	5.8696	4.2644	1.9723

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	525.00	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	70.45	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	284.86	(mm)
PSUB	0.75	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWFL	0.25	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.13	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	0.00	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- River Gauging Station
- Watershed
- Station
- Cities
- Chef Lieu
- Capital
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- Rivers
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SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 050201 RIVIERE JACMEL - JACMEL

MODELED VERSUS HISTORICAL FLOW - MONTHLY AVERAGE VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

Gauge	Flow	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
050401	Modeled	0.5544	0.5278	0.4744	1.3438	2.1426	1.6813	0.9158	1.9447	2.5060	4.0174	1.7210	0.8025
050401	Historical	0.4927	0.4207	0.5276	1.8656	3.9394	3.6327	1.4227	1.0953	1.4973	1.5702	1.3080	0.8594

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	122.30	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	68.63	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	268.66	(mm)
PSUB	0.80	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWF	0.40	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.14	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	10.00	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- River Gauging Station
- Watershed
- Station
- Cities
- Chef Lieu
- Capital
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- Rivers
- Departements

SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 050401 RIVIERE MARIGOT - MARIGOT

GAUGE	FLOW	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
060501	Modeled	1.9965	1.8381	1.2080	2.9298	5.9852	3.4203	2.4053	3.6741	4.3915	5.9438	5.1209	1.4852
060501	Historical	1.9394	1.7882	1.4630	2.1815	4.4258	5.7471	4.1798	3.9736	5.1136	6.3829	11.9736	5.5288

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	64.54	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	63.37	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	231.80	(mm)
PSUB	0.80	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWLF	0.30	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.60	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	65.00	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- River Gauging Station
- Watershed
- Station
- Cities
- Chef Lieu
- Capital
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- Rivers
- Departements

SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 060501 RAVINE DU SUD - CAMP PERRIN

Gauge	Flow	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
060601	Modeled	6.2604	4.6807	2.9438	6.3204	11.3916	8.8809	5.9481	8.4963	11.4458	18.1746	12.8688	6.8976
060601	Historical	4.0766	4.3148	2.8738	4.4990	11.7967	11.6599	4.7735	7.8612	7.3489	19.6391	19.3051	6.1597

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	311.39	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	69.20	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	224.00	(mm)
PSUB	0.80	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWf	0.30	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.15	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	12.00	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- Cities
- Chef Lieu
- Capital
- Roads
- Rivers
- Departements
- Station
- Watershed
- River Gauging Station

SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 060601 RIVIERE CAVAILLON - CAVAILLON

GUAGE	FLOW	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
060801	Modeled	0.1110	0.1044	0.0886	0.1313	0.1562	0.1200	0.1026	0.1868	0.2326	0.4930	0.1839	0.1347
060801	Historical	0.1004	0.0732	0.1194	0.0766	0.0882	0.2996	0.0581	0.2832	0.2144	0.1531	0.0534	0.1577

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	315.50	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	69.42	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	322.12	(mm)
PSUB	0.96	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWf	0.01	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.06	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.00	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	0.00	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- River Gauging Station
- Watershed
- Station
- Cities
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- Capital
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- Rivers
- Departements

SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 060801 RIVIERE COTES DE FER - COTES DE FER

MODELED VERSUS HISTORICAL FLOW - MONTHLY AVERAGE VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

Gauge	Flow	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
070201	Modeled	3.4990	2.9868	1.9661	2.8691	5.9304	3.8948	2.3818	3.4010	4.3655	7.4600	8.3784	4.1343
070201	Historical	2.8930	3.5667	3.3532	6.0072	5.6651	3.4348	1.6965	4.5614	4.1988	3.5871	7.2356	5.0683

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	205.80	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	66.17	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	264.37	(mm)
PSUB	0.80	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWf	0.20	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.09	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	7.50	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- Station
- Watershed
- Cities
- Chef Lieu
- Capital
- Roads
- Rivers
- Departements

SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 070201 RIVIERE VOLDROGUE - PASSE LARAQUE

MODELED VERSUS HISTORICAL FLOW - MONTHLY AVERAGE VALUES (UNIT: CUBIC METER PER SECOND)

Gauge	Flow	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
070301	Modeled	10.3972	8.7641	5.8916	17.7945	34.0985	21.2347	11.4612	20.8516	23.3588	30.8412	29.3098	16.2943
070301	Historical	10.2016	8.3160	11.0595	18.8114	29.2767	23.2895	15.1366	22.3588	15.7911	25.7159	34.9743	15.3668

WATERSHED HYDROLOGIC PARAMETERS

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	563.47	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	67.39	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	281.86	(mm)
PSUB	0.90	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWf	0.20	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.50	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	40.00	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- River Gauging Station
- Watershed
- Station
- Cities
- Chef Lieu
- Capital
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- Rivers
- Departements

SELECTED GAUGING STATION - 070301 RIVIERE GRANDE ANSE - PASSE RANJA

GAUGE	FLOW	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER
099999	Modeled	18.8569	21.7959	19.4632	53.5642	170.0742	139.0754	79.6154	127.9777	157.6923	142.0146	62.3113	28.0179
099999	Historical	26.9900	21.7800	22.4000	44.2100	128.3000	153.4500	92.7500	103.4400	150.1600	165.3900	75.0700	36.5200

PARAMETERS	VALUES	UNIT/DESCRIPTION
Watershed Area	6,700.75	(Sq. km)
SCS-CN	71.80	(SCS - Average Curve Number)
Soil Capacity	269.55	(mm)
PSUB	0.80	(Fraction of Runoff Reaching the Ground Water Layer)
GWf	0.20	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing to River)
GWL	0.00	(Fraction of Ground Water Flowing out of Watershed)
RFLK	0.25	(Excess Runoff attenuation factor)
BFLK	20.01	(Base Flow mm/sq. km/month)

LEGEND

- River Gauging Station
- Watershed
- Station
- Cities
- Chef Lieu
- Capital
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- Rivers
- Departements

SELECTED GAUGING STATION - PELIGRE